

Borut Pretnar

Measuring ductility – some comments and proposals

Abstract: Ductility is emphasized as a prime feature for the technical application of metallic materials beside strength. The elusive nature of the concept of ductility and the current approaches to its measurement are discussed. The influence on ductility of two primary factors, material strength and content of inclusions (second phase particles), are demonstrated on the example of cast iron. The adverse effect of variability of ductility parameters is emphasized and the impact of different tension specimen forms on the variability is demonstrated. The microscopic examination of inclusion content is discussed and the automatic image analysis, based on stereometric parameters, recommended. Some special specimen forms for mechanical testing with promising properties (e. g. easy preparation and/or reduced variability of ductility parameters) are proposed.

Key words: ductility; impact of inclusions on ductility; variability of ductility parameters; measurement of inclusion content; proposals for specimen forms

1. Introductory remarks

The performance of metallic materials intended to withstand mechanical load and/or forming operations rests upon strength and ductility as their two key properties. Strength and ductility are physically quantified as stress and strain, essentially multi-valued tensor quantities difficult to comprehend and interpret. However, while stress is numerically used for dimensional calculations as force per area, ductility remains an elusive concept. It is occasionally defined e. g. as “a *qualitative subjective property of a material*” [1]. It may be loosely defined as the deformation at fracture. There is, however, a noteworthy attempt to devise a *semiquantitative measure of ductility* applied to materials for parts of turbines (e. g. blades) [2].

Ductility is measured by many disparate tightly specified procedures aimed at testing the suitability of materials either for general use or for specific technical applications. Although the test procedures are not directly comparable, they do often produce correlated results. As a rule, the test results cannot be used immediately and numerically in the calculations of structural design – instead, empirically tested and proved results are relied upon. Charpy impact test is a paramount example of this approach.

Ductility depends on many variables, in particular it decreases with increasing strength and with number and size of interior cracks, especially those due to non-metallic inclusions, whose form and spatial distribution also play a role. Of course, there are additional variables as stress state, history of deformation, strain rate, temperature, some microstructural features (e. g. grain size), embrittlement due to environmental factors (e. g. wrong heat treatment, irradiation, intake of hydrogen by diffusion etc).

This article is focused on the two primary factors, non-metallic inclusions and strength. Ferritic-pearlitic cast iron is an outstanding example of dramatic changes of ductility (here quantified as elongation in tension test) due to the varying form of graphite inclusions in the four subspecies of cast iron as well as to the changing strength, see Table 1.

Table 1: adapted from [3] p. 603 table 31.10 and [4] pp. 638, 639 table 14.5.

Cast iron subspecies	Graphite inclusions form	Yield strength N/mm ²	Tensile strength N/mm ²	Fracture elongation ¹ in % L ₀ = 5 d ₀	Fracture elongation in % L ₀ = 50 mm
Grey	Flakes	None ²	100 ... 350	0,8 ... 0,3	Negligible ²
Compacted graphite	Wormlike ³	240 ... 340	300 ... 500	1,5 ... 0,5	3 ... 1
Malleable	Rosettes ⁴	190 ... 340	300 ... 800	10 ... 1	10 ... 6
Ductile (nodular)	Nodules ⁵	220 ... 600	350 ... 900	32 ... 2	18 ... 2

¹ Proportional gage length amounts to five specimen diameters.

² Tensile loading ends with brittle fracture.

³ Wormlike inclusions with rare interspersed round ones

⁴ Circular clusters of small irregularly shaped particles

⁵ Smoothly rounded inclusions

The advent of the fracture mechanics was a paradigm shift in design philosophy, previously based mainly on the concept of (linear elastic) notch stress concentration, occasionally modified for plastic relaxation at the tip of the notch [1]. However, although fracture mechanics is a modern science branch in its own right, it is fraught with some scholastic flavour due to the sophisticated testing procedures and mathematical complexities. This holds true particularly for the concepts beyond the simple (linear elastic) fracture toughness K_{Ic} , i. e. corrections for plasticity via COD (crack opening displacement) or for the J-integral. As a consequence, it is better applicable on materials with limited ductility. It seems that physicists with their advanced mathematical skills are in a better position for its study and application than metallurgical practitioners dealing with quickly testable technical specifications in the production quality control.

2. The effect of inclusions on ductility of steels

Structural steels, an important and widely used material, are frequently infested with non-metallic inclusions (mainly sulphides and/or oxides) of various size, form and number, acting as cracks. They decrease ductility and may cause its anisotropy due to the preferred orientation acquired during hot forming (rolling, forging). The effect of inclusions is usually measured by the two main ductility parameters obtained in tension test, i. e. elongation and reduction of area (briefly EL and RA). The textbook [5] explicitly explains that *“in the general sense, elongation and reduction of area measure different types of material behaviour”*.

Elongation is the result of two consecutive processes occurring during tension test, i. e. first uniform elongation and second elongation during necking (i. e. local contraction of the cross-section). Reduction of area is closely connected only with the latter because necking occurs near the fracture site. The nature and quantitative relation between the EL and RA is studied in detail e. g. in [6]. The textbook [5] recommends RA as an appropriate measure for ductility (although there is no direct method to incorporate it in design).

In plates and sheets, there are three mutually orthogonal directions with significantly different effect of inclusions on ductility: longitudinal (the direction of rolling), transverse, and short transverse (or “through thickness”, briefly TT), i.e. the direction orthogonal to the two flat surfaces. Reduction of area is usually ranked in the order: lowest in the TT direction, intermediate in transverse direction and highest in the longitudinal direction [5];[6]. A study of the TTRA range and TTRA dependence on strength and inclusion content is given in [7a]. In steels substantially infested with non-metallic inclusions the TTRA does not exhibit only the lowest value but also the highest variability exceeding five to ten times the adjacent longitudinal and transverse values [7b]. The TTRA variability (e. g. its standard deviation) may also depend on TTRA average value in an unexpected and unexplained way [7b]. Additional (sometimes overlooked) criteria should be considered at ductility measurement, notably its ability to determine the ductility parameters *with the desired precision (repeatability and reproducibility)* of their own value and also of the difference between their values in different directions. Excessive variability (dispersion) of the measured results may either render these goals impossible or make an unacceptable number of sampling units necessary. The choice (or creation) of an appropriate specimen form can substantially reduce the variability of results. An example is the study [8] where the difference between the longitudinal and transverse ductility was measured by elongation. Two specimen forms, unnotched and notched, were used. The longitudinal-transverse difference of elongations of the *notched* specimens proved as a much better discerning measure than the elongation difference of the *unnotched* specimens. Note that the elongation around the notch occurs in close vicinity of the fracture site. Consequently, the elongation in this case is predominantly the result of the necking process and as such well correlated with the (actually not measured) RA. In addition, the position of fracture is fixed at the centre of the specimen and any undesirable eccentricity of fracture (e. g. outside the gauge length), invalidating the test, is avoided [9].

The above line of reasoning was upgraded with an enlarged study [10] including five hot rolled steel sheets 2,5 ... 3 mm thick with yield strength 330 ... 450 N/mm² and widely differing inclusion content. Several flat specimen forms were prepared and tension tested:

- a) three types of standard unnotched forms
- b) one V-notched and
- c) one with a specially invented form, sketched in fig. 1

Figure 1: The invented tension specimen used in study [10]

RA was tested on all forms, EL on all except the invented one.

The invented specimen was perforated by two symmetric adjacent circular holes (3 mm diam.) leaving between them a metal “bridge” with square cross section where it was thinnest, i. e. the material thickness and width of the “bridge” were made equal where the holes were nearest. This was the predetermined site for fracture where RA was measured. (Note that the RA of a curved “bridge” - and generally on any notched site - is not equal to the RA of the unnotched specimen). In addition, the measurement of RA was applied to thickness below 4 mm. (The usual round specimens are machined only above 4mm diameter). An advanced statistical method (nonparametric Kruskal-Wallis test) was used for the evaluation of results. The RA of the specially invented specimen form proved to exhibit by far the least variability, followed by the RA of the V-notched specimen form. Elongation measurements (of the same number of samples) proved inconclusive.

3. Measurement of inclusion content

Reference [11] presents a general review of inclusion measurement. Numerous international [12;13] and national [14;15] standards prescribe procedures for measurement of inclusion content. Unfortunately, the traditional measures based on the comparison of microscopic observations to standardized charts do not lend themselves to an appropriate numerical quantification, necessary to enable treatment of results by the methods of mathematical statistics. Statistical treatment is unavoidable in order to make objective differentiation and quality ranking possible. Study [16] demonstrated that measures of inclusion content based on charts according to ASTM E45 are fraught with poor reproducibility and precision. Therefore, measurements of inclusion content should be based on stereometric parameters [17];[18]. Contemporary automated image analysis offers fast and convenient measurement of stereometric parameters preventing subjective errors of observers [15].

Relevant stereometric parameters include e. g. volume fraction of inclusions and their projected length per area ($\mu\text{m}/\text{mm}^2$) measured e. g. in the study [7a] in addition to ductility parameters. Other parameters as the number of inclusions per area, their average length (μm), fraction of area (as an estimate of volume fraction), average area, and mean free

distance between inclusions (μm) also contain information about their spatial distribution and shape. Some promising stereometric parameters (or combination of them) may still be invented [18] and tested. The parameters of the inclusion content should be as closely as possible correlated with the mechanically measured ductility parameters. However, full and reliable replacement of the mechanical measured ductility by microstructure examination remains a challenge. It would be especially welcome where the cumbersome preparation of tension specimens is needed for the acceptance decision as e. g. the TTRA testing according to ASTM A770 [19].

4. Inventing specimen forms

The results of the study [10] foster further experimentation with specimen forms in order to develop ductility tests characterized by small variability of results, simple specimen preparation - or both, if possible. Of course, this implies the (unfamiliar) demand that ductility and strength be measured on separate specimens. Some ideas (which the writer of this article was not empowered to carry out) may be as follows:

- A modified variant of the perforated flat specimen used in the study [10] and sketched in fig.1: not only two but several adjacent holes may be drilled in a series, producing kind of “zipper-like” fracture. This is essentially an evenly distributed “notch” across the specimen width. Here it is possible to measure multiple values of RA and, if desired, EL on a relatively short gauge length.
- Flat tensile specimen with a circular hole which during tension extends to an elliptical hole: the initial radius changes its value to the axes of the ellipse. The geometric difference may provide the measure of ductility. The hole may be quite small (in mm-range) and positioned on the specified spot in material where the properties rapidly change with position, e. g. in the heat-affected zone beside a weld.
- Flat tensile specimen with two thin (say 1mm or less) lateral cuts (symmetric notches) on both sides, see fig. 2: during tension testing the notches will (probably) open up. The opening angle “ α ” or the opening distance “d” may be measured as the ductility parameter. (The method is actually mimicking the COD concept known in fracture mechanics). As an additional idea also the asymmetric case (one cut on one side only) could be tested. Round specimens lend themselves with a round notch.

Figure 2: Tension specimen with lateral cuts, initial and fractured

The difficult measurement of TTRA in steel plates is described in the standard ASTM A770 [19]. The value of TTRA above some level, usually 20%, must be achieved to prevent the harmful occurrence of *lamellar tearing*. *Lamellar tearing* is according to Appendix 1 of the standard “a particular type of cracking that occurs under the weld of a steel plate weldment ... in a direction generally parallel to the plate surface and often slightly outside the heat-affected zone.» Non-metallic inclusions are believed to be the primary cause.

The through-thickness tensile specimens need prolongations, attached by welding to the ends of samples (i. e. »coupons«, cut out from plates in the full thickness between planar surfaces) in order to provide holds for specimens mounted in tension testing device. In addition, high variability of TTRA results sometimes casts doubts on acceptance decision.

Simpler approaches for testing the harmful presence of non-metallic inclusions may supplement (or substitute?) the actual cumbersome procedure. The proposed specimen forms (cube-like and plate-like) intended for compression and bend tests, respectively, are sketched in fig. 3. (Instead of cube a cylindrical specimen of approximately equal diameter and height could be submitted to axial compression.) Compression load is supposed to be exerted in the longitudinal or transverse direction. The crack-prone orientation of the specimens is shown in fig. 3. Occurrence of cracks at some predefined strain could serve as an auxiliary information for acceptance decision.

Figure 3: Position of cube-like and plate-like specimens for compression and bend test, respectively

5. References

[1] American Society for Metals (ASM): Ductility – Papers presented at a Seminar of the ASM October 14 and 15, 1967

ASM 1968

Dieter, George E.: Introduction to Ductility pp. 1- 30

[2] Huff, H.: Zeitschrift für Werkstoffkunde/J. of Materials Technology **7** (1976) pp. 298-299
 “Ansätze für ein Zähigkeitskriterium/An Approach to Ductility Criterion” (in German).

[3] Bender, B., D. Göhlich eds.:

Dubbel – Taschenbuch für den Maschinenbau Band 1 Grundlagen und Tabellen
 (Handbook of Mechanical Engineering Part 1 Foundations and Tables) in German
 Springer Vieweg 26th ed. 2020

[4] Callister, W. D., D. G. Rethwisch:

Fundamentals of Material Science and Engineering
 International Adaptation – SI Version
 Wiley, 6th ed. 2022

[5] Dieter, George E.: Mechanical Metallurgy

Mc Graw-Hill 3rd ed. 1986 pp. 293-295; 322 - 324

- [6] Ludwigson, D. C., M. M. McDonald:
J. of Testing and Evaluation Vol. 12 No.5 Sept. 1984 pp. 288-296
“Quantitative Relations Among Measures of Ductility in Planar and Through-Thickness Tension Tests of 12.8-mm-Diameter Specimens”
- [7] Glodowski, R. J. ed.: ASTM STP 794, Through-Thickness Tension Testing of Steel
American Society for Testing and Materials (ASTM) 1983
a) Ludwigson D. C.: “Relation of Through-Thickness Ductility to Inclusion Prevalence, Matrix Toughness, and Matrix Strength” pp. 113-120
b) Ludwigson, D. C.: “Factors Affecting Variability in Through-Thickness Reduction-of-Area Measurements” pp. 40 – 46
- [8] Sonne, H. M., B. Pretnar, W. Müschenborn:
Arch. Eisenhüttenwes. 50 (1979) Nr. 12 pp. 503-508
»Notched tensile test and stretch bend test – testing methods for characterizing the cold formability of hot and cold rolled steel sheet products« (in German)
- [9] Pretnar, B., R. A. N. Yebuah:
Materialprüfung 29 (1987) Nr. 4 pp. 104-105
»A study of the effect of tensile specimens form on the eccentricity of fracture«
- [10] Pretnar, B., R. A. N. Yebuah:
J. of Testing and Evaluation Vol. 16 No. 3 (May 1988) pp. 305-311
»Effect of Nonmetallic Inclusions on Some Ductility Parameters of Hot-Rolled Steel«
- [11] McCall, J.L., French, P.M. eds.: Metallography as a Quality Control Tool
Vander Voort, G.F. “Inclusion Measurement” pp. 1-88
Springer 1980
- [12] ISO 4967: 2013
Steel – Determination of content of non-metallic inclusions – Micrographic method using standard diagrams
- [13] EN 10247 (2007)
Micrographic examination of the nonmetallic inclusion content of steels using standard pictures
- [14] ASTM E45 – 25
Standard Test Methods for Determining the Inclusion Content in Steel
- [15] ASTM E1245-23
Standard Practice for Determining the Inclusion as Second-Phase Constituent Content of Metals by Automatic Image Analysis

[16] Vander Voort, G. F.: Materials Performance and Characterization 5 (December 2016)
Issue 5 pp. 510 -520

»Results of Interlaboratory Test Programs to Assess the Precision of Inclusion Ratings by
Methods A, C, and D of ASTM E45«

<https://doi.org/10.1520/MPC20160002>

[17] ASM Handbook (formerly Metals Handbook) Vol. 9 Metallography and Microstructures-
Metallographic Techniques

E. E. Underwood: "Quantitative Metallography" pp. 125-134

ASM (American Society for Metals) International 9th ed. 1985

[18] Ohser, J., F. Mücklich:

Statistical Analysis of Microstructures in Material Science

Wiley/VCH 2000

[19] ASTM A770/A770M – 03 (2012)

Standard Specification for Through-Thickness Tension Testing of Steel Plates for
Special Applications